

MELILOTUS OFFICINALIS

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The antimicrobial effect of the methanolic extract of *Melilotus officinalis* was investigated against Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria. MIC against *Escherichia coli*: 15mg, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*: 18mg, *Proteus mirabilis*: 20mg, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: 25mg, *Staphylococcus aureus*: 25mg, *Streptococcus pyogenes*: 30mg, *Bacillus subtilis*: 25mg, *Bacillus cereus*: 25 mg and *Candida albicans* 35mg. The antibacterial activity of the water, acetone, diethyl ether and ethanol extracts of *Melilotus officinalis* was studied against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Salmonella enteric*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Sarcina lutea*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bifidobacterium animalis subsp. lactis* and *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*. The values of MIC and MMC were in a range of <0.156 mg/ml to >20 mg/ml. The intensity of antibacterial activity depended on the type of extract and the type of bacteria. The extracts were active in the following ascending order: water < ethanol < diethyl ether < acetone. The acetone and the diethyl ether were the most active extracts, while water and ethanol extracts showed significantly lower activity. Gram negative bacteria showed higher sensitivity to the acetone and diethyl ether extracts, but never in concentrations less than 10 mg/ml for MIC and MMC, except for *Escherichia coli* which was sensitive in the concentration of 5 mg/ml of the ether extract for MIC. The antibacterial effect of the aqueous, methanolic and ethanolic extract of *Melilotus officinalis* was

investigated against Gram negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and Gram positive bacteria (*Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*). The ethanolic extract of *Melilotus officinalis* showed more antibacterial effect than aqueous and methanolic extracts against *S. marcescens* and *S. typhimurium*. *P. vulgaris*, *E. cloacae*, and *E. coli* were susceptible to aqueous extract of *Melilotus officinalis*. However, all the tested bacteria were not susceptible to methanolic extracts. In vitro antifungal activities of *Melilotus officinalis* extracts were evaluated against *C. inconspicua*, *C. guilliermondii*, *C. albicans*, *C. krusei*, *C. lusitaniae*, *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis*, *C. methapsilosis*, and *C. ortopsilosis*. The results showed that *Melilotus officinalis* extracts were active antimycotic agents against wide range of *Candida* species. *C. guilliermondii* and *C. parapsilosis* were the most sensitive.

Dermatological effect: In studying the beneficial effect of the extract of *Melilotus officinalis* in skin care applications, the extract showed an ability of stimulating skin cells and promoting tissue regeneration, preventing skin aging,

and reducing fat deposition. The effects of ethanolic extract at doses ranging from 0.25 to 50 µg/ml (from 1 to 5000 µg/ml in cell viability assays) were evaluated using in vitro tests on HaCaT human keratinocytes, 46BR 1N fibroblasts, and adipocyte cell cultures, and on matrix-degrading enzymes. MTT assay revealed weak effects on cell viability ($IC_{50} > 1000$ µg/ml) and significant increase of fibroblast growth rate. Cell-free enzymatic assays showed collagenase inhibition, while an ELISA assay revealed efficient stimulation of fibroblast collagen production. Oil-Red-O adipocyte staining showed pronounced lipolytic effect. The effects of *Melilotus officinalis* ointment in the healing of burn wounds were studied in burn ulcers produced on the back of rats. Wound healing contraction and histopathological examination were evaluated at the end of 7, 14, and 21 days. *Melilotus officinalis* preparations significantly improved the quality of wound healing and scar formation and also they were more appropriate treatment choices than silver sulfadiazine.

Использованная литература:

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